

THE INTERACTION OF NITROUS ACID WITH THIOCARBAMIDES AND AMIDES. CONSTITUTION OF THE SO-CALLED FORMAMIDINE DISULPHIDE

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Action of nitrous acid on thiocarbamide has been discussed in the light of its interaction with amides, methylamine and ammonia. An examination of the gases evolved during these changes has shown that there is no reason to assume a tautomeric change in thiocarbamide. Its behaviour towards nitrous acid in weak and strong acid media respectively, is comparable with the oxidation of diphenylamine in a neutral and strongly acidic medium. This affords some indirect evidence for a non-disulphide constitution for "formamidine disulphide".

It has been suggested in another communication (to be published later) that 'formamidine disulphide', which can be most easily obtained by the oxidation of thiocarbamide by a variety of oxidising agents including nitrous acid, may not have a truly disulphide constitution (cf. this *Journal*, 1945, 22, 37). Since Werner and Krall (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 2180; 1917, 111, 863; this *Journal*, 1935, 12, 640; 1937, 14, 478; 1938, 15, 217) have extensively used nitrous acid as a reagent in their studies supporting tautomerism of thiocarbamides, and therefore indirectly also the formation of disulphides from them, a re-examination of the rationale of their procedure appeared of interest. The reagent has been used on the assumptions: (i) nitrous acid reacts quantitatively with an amino group evolving nitrogen and (ii) if any alteration in the experimental conditions (usually p_H) alters the amount of nitrogen evolved, this may be taken both as an indication and measure of the tautomerism of the substance under examination. In weak acid medium, like dilute acetic acid, the structure of thiocarbamides, according to these authors, is truly carbamidic, therefore, they liberate nitrogen by the action of nitrous acid on their amino groups; in a strong acid medium the $-NH_2$ groups change over into $-NH$ due to tautomerism and so no nitrogen is evolved under this condition. Plimmer, on the other hand, working with a number of amides showed (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2651) that they unlike the thiocarbamides did not evolve nitrogen in a weak acid medium like the acetic acid, but in a mineral acid medium readily gave this gas. Yet, this author also from his investigations concluded tautomerism in the amides. Krall (this *Journal*, 1939, 16, 9), who studied the decomposition of ammonium nitrite under precisely the same conditions in which the action of nitrous acid on thiocarbamides had been investigated, obtained results very much similar to those with the latter. Results of the present author's experiments (*vide infra*, Table I) with methylamine, ammonium chloride and acetate, thiocarbamide and its ethyl and phenyl homologues, clearly indicate that notwithstanding the wide variety of compounds selected, there is a distinct evenness in these results. Evidently, tautomerism cannot be the chief determinant of this phenomenon.

TABLE I

No.	Name of the compound.	Acetic acid medium			Hydrochloric acid medium.			Duration of expt.
		Total gas.	%N ₂ .	%NO.	Total gas.	%N ₂ .	%NO.	
1	Me.NH ₂ .HCl	18.25c.c.	80.1	19.9	14.74c.c.	3.3 *	96.7	24 hrs.
2	Do	18.3	78.3	21.7	14.68	3.3	96.7	"
3	NH ₄ Cl				14.4	29.0	71.0	"
4	NH ₄ Ac	11.56	77.7	22.3				"
5	H ₂ N.CS.NH ₂	22.2	91.4	8.6	22.2	12.0	88.0	"
6	PhNH.CS.NH ₂	22.3	75.9	24.1	22.2	9.5	90.5	"
7	EtNH.CS.NH ₂	22.4	74.5	24.5		3.0	97.0	"

All these experiments were carried out with milligram molar proportions of the reactant in 1:1 ratio. The technique was essentially the same as followed by Werner and Krall *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

Investigations with methylamine and ammonium chloride have clearly indicated (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 515) that the rate of the reaction between the amino group and nitrous acid is largely controlled by the acidity of the medium. It was then pointed out that the differential behaviour of thiocarbamides (and amides in general) towards nitrous acid in weak and strong acid media respectively, might be, as with amines, due to greater or less susceptibility (which varied with the acidity of the medium) of the amino group to react and not tautomerism. Results in Table I only further substantiate this view.

FIG. 1

Coade and Werner (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 113, 1221) investigated the influence of p_a on the interaction of nitrous acid and thiocarbamide over a wide range. These authors used a variety of acids to vary the acidity of

the medium. The great regularity evinced in their work in the dependence of nitrogen evolution on the dissociation constants of the acids, itself supports the view now put forth. If the phenomenon involved were of tautomerism, such regularity with a variety of acids could not be expected, except perhaps, as coincidence. Similarity in curves 1 and 2 in Fig. 1 depicting the results of Coade and Werner and those of the present author with thiocarbamide and methylamine respectively, further indicates that the mechanism of both these changes is most probably identical.

From these facts it is clear that Werner's original assumptions (*vide supra*), though not wholly untenable, need modification. It appears that the differential behaviour of thiocarbamide and amides in general, towards nitrous acid in weak and strong acid media respectively might be (i) as with amines, due to the greater or less susceptibility (which varied with the acidity of the medium and consequent salt formation) of the amino group to react and (ii) constitutional factors not necessarily tautomerism. That thiocarbamide, methylamine and ammonium chloride interact more or less similarly with nitrous acid is well indicated by the investigations reported already (*loc. cit.*).

The interaction of thiocarbamide and nitrous acid has been known to proceed under the two conditions :

In a weak acid medium

In a strong medium

There is no reasonable doubt about the quantitative aspect of these changes, but the question is whether or not in (ii) a tautomeric change precedes oxidation and the product obtained is a disulphide? The same oxidation product, viz. the "formamidine disulphide", has been shown to be formed in an indifferent solvent medium (this *Journal*, 1950, 27, 431 : also in a paper on the interaction of bromine with thiocarbamide, communicated) and in a pure aqueous* medium; there is no reason therefore to assume (Werner, *loc. cit.*) that a strong acid brings about the tautomeric change. Further, thiocarbamide has two $-\text{NH}_2$ groups and if by tautomerism, assuming this to be prevalent, one of them changes over to $:\text{NH}$, the other $-\text{NH}_2$ should still react with nitrous acid to give nitrogen, which it does not. Then thiocarbamide does not also give a *N*-nitroso derivative which it ought to if it had a $:\text{NH}$ under any of the above conditions. These facts further support the view now put forth that it is the capacity of the $-\text{NH}_2$ group to react with nitrous acid that determines the course of the reaction.

It appears to the author that in the change (ii), outlined above, the NH_2 groups or their hydrogens do not partake at all, but the reaction takes place at the thiocarbonyl sulphur atom (not the tautomerigenic thiol) resulting in the

abstraction of an electron from the molecule as a whole and forming formamiline disulphide" which has been suggested to have the constitution $(H_2N.CS.NH_2)-X$ and not the one hitherto assigned to it. The reaction recalls the behaviour of diphenylamine which can be oxidised in two ways (Sidgwick, Taylor and Baker, "Organic Chemistry of Nitrogen", Oxford University Press, Reprint, 1942, p. 62), 'at the imino group in neutral solution and at the p -carbon atom in a strongly acid solution. Thus :

In neutral or weakly acidic media the imino or the amino groups of these compounds (viz. diphenylamine and thiocarbamide) are in a feebly charged condition only owing to the inherent attraction exerted on the electrons by the phenyl or the thiocarbonyl groups. In a strongly acid medium, this tendency is both complemented and completed resulting in the fixation of a positive charge on the imino or the amino groups. This, however, at the same time results in an increased concentration of electrons at the p -carbon atom or sulphur, thereby shifting the reactivity from the amino group to sulphur or the p -carbon atom. The loss of the reactivity of the \oplus ive NH_2 ions may also be due to decreased possibilities of co-ordination at the nitrogen since it has already co-ordinated a proton.

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